

Rhetorical Moves in Presidential Victory Speeches: Spotlighting a Non-native Speaker Context

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Abstract

Presidential speeches, particularly victory speeches (VSs), represent a distinctive genre within political discourse, reflecting national identity, persuasive strategies, and leadership ethos. Existing research on presidential speech genres has analysed their rhetorical structures, linguistic features, and ideological functions, mainly in Western or pan-African contexts. However, little attention has been paid to Ghanaian presidents' VSs as a genre. This study, therefore, investigates the schematic structure of the VSs delivered by four presidents of Ghana's Fourth Republic. Swales's (1990) move/step analysis was utilised as the analytical framework, and Huttner's (2010) model was employed to determine the status of each move. A qualitative research design was adopted to facilitate an in-depth exploration of the generic structure and the communicative functions of the identified moves. The findings demonstrate that Ghanaian presidents' VSs are characterised by a four-move structure: *saluting*, *thanking*, *appealing to the audience*, and *closing*. We must stress that these moves appear in a linear sequence in the data. Also, the thanking move occupies the most textual space. In contrast, the saluting move occupies the least space, suggesting that a VS primarily serves as an avenue for a president-elect to express appreciation for the electorate's overwhelming support. The findings contribute to scholarship on political discourse, with particular emphasis on presidential VSs and genre studies.

Keywords

Genre analysis, Ghana, schematic structure, presidential victory speeches

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Introduction

Spoken or written texts that address political issues, such as VSs, constitute political discourse (Van Dijk, 1996). As Al-Faki (2014) opined, political discourse encompasses a range of genres, including inaugural speeches, policy papers, government press releases, party manifestos, campaign messages, and victory speeches. It must be stressed that each political speech genre serves a unique communicative purpose. VS, in particular, is delivered by the president-elect to express gratitude to the electorate following the announcement of the election results. It aims to inspire supporters of the winning candidate, reach out to those who did not vote for the winner, and convey appreciation and hope for a nation's future.

Dufour et al. (2009) argue that VSs may be either scripted or spontaneous. When VSs are spontaneous, they are often characterised by pauses, false starts, and repetitions, whereas scripted ones are well prepared and rehearsed (Boakye, 2014). Mwinwelle et al. (2019) postulate that even candidates who lose elections still deliver concession speeches. For example, in the Ghanaian context, Presidents Akufo-Addo and John Mahama accepted defeat in the 2012 and 2016 general elections, respectively, and delivered their concession speeches. Other selected instances across the globe include Kamala Harris' 2024 concession speech delivered after losing the 2024 American General Elections, the concession speech given by Rishi Sunak in 2020 after losing to Keir Starmer in the UK elections, Judith Collins' concession speech delivered in 2020 after losing the New Zealand General Elections and Keiko Fujimori's 2021 Concession Speech delivered after losing the Peru General Elections. It is argued that politicians use words to position themselves as favourites, even when delivering concession speeches. Unlike concession speeches, VSs constitute acknowledgements to the electorate and are delivered before an inaugural speech. In Ghana, VSs are delivered in English despite the numerous indigenous languages spoken. Hyland (2011) argues that English remains the language of international scholarship. Given Hyland's (2011) argument and the fact that English is the official language in Ghana, Ghanaian elected presidents are not indifferent to the use of English to deliver VSs.

Studies in political discourse have examined various presidential communication genres, including campaign messages (Benoit, 2007; Liu, 2012), inaugural speeches (Charteris-Black, 2011; Pagliarini, 2011), concession speeches (Chilton, 2004; Weber, 2011), and party manifestos of presidents worldwide (Green & Hobolt, 2014; Panebianco, 2010). In Ghana, several studies on political discourse have sought to describe and analyse the style of politicians (Adjei-Fobi, 2012), their creative and persuasive tactics (Boakye, 2014; Mwinwelle et al., 2019), and how they manipulate linguistic expressions to promote personal interests in presidential speeches (Anderson, 2014; Asare et al., 2026). However, post-election VSs have gained very little scholarly attention in the Ghanaian context. Very few studies on presidential victory speeches have been conducted outside the African continent (Chanturidze, 2018; Irimiea, 2010; Liu & Zhang, 2018), within Africa, particularly in Nigeria (Acheoah, Balogun, & Waziri, 2023; Ayeomoni & Akinkuolere, 2012; Sharndama & Mgbemana, 2015), and in Ghana, where few studies have examined victory speeches, notably on personal deictic expressions (Asare et al., 2025). Accordingly, there is a paucity of scholarship on presidential VSs, despite the growing interest among

discourse analysts, scholars, and researchers in political speech genres from multi-party nations such as Ghana. VVs remain understudied in Ghanaian discourse; hence, their investigation is crucial. The current study aims to fill this knowledge gap by employing genre-based theory to examine the schematic structure of the VVs of four Ghanaian presidents, thereby elucidating the conventional and context-sensitive organisational patterns that characterise post-election presidential discourse in Ghana.

1. Theoretical Lens: The Genre Theory

The word “genre” is derived from the French language and means “kind” or “class”. Bawarishi and Reiff (2010) argue that, since genre analysis has recently transformed in its role in the interpretation and creation of discourse, it has shifted from a descriptive to an explanatory activity. It has long been used to refer to a variety of artistic and literary works. To classify language use and communication in many facets of life, linguists and language educators have recently expanded genre studies. Nonetheless, since the 1970s, genre has become a potent tool for evaluating both literary and non-literary discourse, piquing the interest of a wide range of disciplines because it not only depicts the external characteristics of discourse but also reveals its underlying principle (Zhan, 2012).

Since the 1970s, the term “*genre*” has evolved into a more nuanced and multi-layered understanding of the macro-structures and communicative functions of discourse; thus, genre analysis has emerged as an important branch of discourse analysis (Liu, 2012). Afful and Tekpetey (2011) posit that though the term genre dates as far back as the Graeco-Roman era, it is only in recent times that it has been popularised, especially in the field of Applied Linguistics due to the studies of scholars such as Swales (1990), Miller (1984), and Martin (2002). This branch of linguistics has been applied to academic and other professional activities and events.

Swales (1990) defines genre as “a class of communicative events, the members of which share some set of communicative purposes” (p. 58), and argues that these purposes constitute the genre’s rationale and shape its schematic structure, influencing choices of content and style. Swales further explains that moves characterise a genre and help classify a particular text as that genre. A move is a sub-rhetorical unit within a text, and a step is a sub-move or optional move within a move (Hyland, 2004; Bhatia, 1993). Central to genre theory is the notion of the discourse community, which provides the social and institutional context within which genres are produced and interpreted. According to Swales (1990), a discourse community is characterised by shared goals, specialised genres, and conventions that regulate how communicative purposes are realised. In this sense, genres are not merely formal templates but socially recognised ways of using language that members of a community draw upon to accomplish recurrent communicative actions. Within such communities, genres stabilise over time through repeated use, making certain rhetorical moves obligatory or core, while others remain optional or context-dependent (Afful & Gyasi, 2020). Core or obligatory moves are those essential for fulfilling a genre’s communicative purpose and whose absence may compromise genre recognition, whereas optional moves allow flexibility and variation depending on context, audience, and speaker intention (Bhatia, 1993; Hyland, 2004). The communicative purposes of a genre are realised in the moves employed by the speaker. These moves are the various ways

a speaker manoeuvres to make intentions known to the audience. Genres are realised in moves, and political speeches are not different. Speakers carefully organise their thoughts and messages in moves to achieve the total intention of the event. For the above reasons, the researchers adopt Swales' (1990) genre analysis framework to examine the schematic structures that characterise VSs of Ghanaian presidents under the Fourth Republic.

2. Related Studies

Genre-based approaches have been widely applied in the analysis of political discourse across different geopolitical contexts. Several studies have examined the rhetorical organisation of political texts such as manifestos, inaugural speeches, and debates using frameworks derived from Swales and Bhatia. For example, Sarvat (2021) employed Swales' (1990) CARS model to investigate the generic structure of the Pakistan People's Party (PPP) manifesto. The study showed that ideology-related moves occurred more frequently than other moves, indicating that political manifestos are designed to shape ideological orientations at the grassroots level. Similarly, Pagliarini (2011) examined Barack Obama's inaugural address using rhetorical and genre analysis and demonstrated how conventional and unconventional rhetorical strategies interact to produce persuasive effects. Although these studies analyse different political genres, both highlight the persuasive and ideological functions of rhetorical moves in political communication.

Research has also examined the schematic structure of presidential speeches using larger corpora. Weber (2011), for instance, analysed 56 U.S. inaugural speeches through a computer-assisted approach and observed increasing standardisation in obligatory moves such as greetings, calls for national renewal, and reaffirmations of collective values. These findings suggest that the realisation of rhetorical moves in political speeches is influenced by communicative context, audience expectations, and institutional conventions. In a similar vein, Zhan (2012) analysed 28 prepared political debates using Bhatia's (1993) framework and found that rhetorical moves may vary depending on the speaker's communicative intentions. Liu (2012), studying American inaugural speeches, also identified consistent rhetorical move patterns serving distinct communicative functions. Together, these studies demonstrate that political speech genres often exhibit recognisable schematic structures, reinforcing the usefulness of move analysis in understanding rhetorical organisation.

Other scholars have emphasised the role of context and culture in shaping political discourse. Yuan (2005), for example, analysed political speeches by state officials using models proposed by Martin (1986) and Hasan (1978) and concluded that political speeches are influenced by situational context and broader cultural factors. This observation aligns with Weber's (2011) findings that the rhetorical structure of American inaugural speeches evolved in response to changing socio-political conditions. These studies suggest that while political speeches may follow identifiable rhetorical patterns, their schematic organisation remains sensitive to cultural, institutional, and historical contexts.

Studies conducted within the African context have also applied genre analysis to political discourse. In Ghana, for instance, Afful and Gyasi (2020) analysed manifesto launch speeches of three political parties and identified a nine-move structure, including several ambiguous moves that varied according to the speaker's rhetorical strategy. Similarly,

Kyei et al. (2020) examined President Akufo-Addo’s 2017 inaugural speech using Swales’ (1990) and Bhatia’s (1993) models and identified eight rhetorical moves, highlighting the strategic use of inclusive pronouns to engage a national audience. These studies demonstrate that genre analysis is a useful tool for examining rhetorical organisation in African political speeches and reveal that political speakers often combine conventional genre structures with context-specific rhetorical strategies.

Despite these contributions, little attention has been given to presidential victory speeches as a distinct genre within political discourse. Most existing studies focus on manifestos, inaugural speeches, debates, or concession speeches, leaving victory speeches understudied. In the Ghanaian context, research on political discourse has examined rhetorical devices, stylistic features, or persuasive strategies rather than the schematic organisation of victory speeches. Given the ceremonial and persuasive importance of victory speeches in legitimising electoral outcomes, promoting national unity, and outlining political direction after elections, their rhetorical structure warrants systematic scholarly attention. The present study addresses this gap by examining the schematic organisation of presidential victory speeches delivered in Ghana’s Fourth Republic. Drawing on Swales’ (1990) move analysis and Hüttner’s (2010) model for determining move status, the study explores how rhetorical moves are structured within this relatively underexamined political genre.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study utilises a descriptive qualitative research design, primarily because it is more descriptive, although some statistics are used to account for the distribution of moves and textual space. A qualitative research design focuses on understanding social and linguistic phenomena through detailed descriptions and contextual analysis rather than statistical measurements (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). Muijs (2004) and Babbie (2004) emphasise that this approach relies on non-numerical data and naturalistic inquiry to explore how people make sense of their experiences. Afful and Tekpetey (2011) further highlight its usefulness for analysing complex linguistic behaviours in real-world contexts, making it especially suitable for discourse-focused studies like the present one. Denzin and Lincoln (2008) affirm that this approach enables the analysis of social and political occurrences and the interpretations attached to them. Given that the study examines the contextual use of language in Ghanaian presidential victory speeches, a qualitative design is most appropriate.

3.2. Data Source and Collection

The primary data for the study consisted of four (4) presidential victory speeches. Except for the speech of John Dramani Mahama (JDM), the texts of the other three presidents—Nana Addo Dankwa Akufo-Addo (NADAA), John Agyekum Kufuor (JAK), and John Evans Atta Mills (JEAM)—were sourced from <https://www.modernghana.com>, an online media outlet. President Mahama’s victory speech was accessed via the YouTube channel

(<https://youtu.be/IYj0vFRf4gM>) and transcribed for analysis, as the official script was not available. During transcription, features of spontaneous speech such as pauses, hesitations, repetitions, and false starts were omitted, since they were deemed irrelevant to the analysis of the speeches' schematic structure. The analysed speeches were the first victory addresses delivered after each president's election: JAK (2001), JEAM (2009), JDM (2012), and NADAA (2016). Although JDM, JAK, and NADAA each delivered two victory addresses, only those delivered during their initial election as presidents-elect were chosen to ensure comparability, given that JEAM served only one term and delivered a single victory speech. The dataset includes four speeches, as first-term presidential victory addresses are limited in Ghana's Fourth Republic. Victory speeches occur only once following a successful election, which constrains the number of available texts. Therefore, the study employs a purposive sampling strategy centred on these speeches to conduct an in-depth genre-based analysis of their rhetorical organisation within the Ghanaian political context.

3.3 Data Analysis Procedure

This study adopted Swales' (1990) move/step analysis and Hüttner's (2010) model to identify rhetorical moves and determine their status in the victory speeches. These approaches were complemented by the semantic-functional criterion, which determines rhetorical structure based on communicative purpose (Bhatia, 2002). The analysis focused on three aspects of the rhetorical structure: the frequency of moves, their textual space, and their sequencing. Move identification was guided by the communicative function of each textual segment. Each speech was examined to determine the rhetorical purpose of its sections, and segments performing similar communicative functions were grouped into moves and sub-moves (steps). The speeches were analysed through multiple iterative readings to ensure consistency in move identification. Coding decisions were cross-checked among the researchers to minimise interpretive bias and to establish systematic move boundaries.

After identifying the moves, their distribution was analysed in three ways. First, the frequency of each move and step was calculated and organised into frequency and percentage tables. Second, move sequencing was examined by analysing the order in which moves appeared in each speech in order to identify recurrent patterns across the dataset. Third, textual space was measured by counting the number of words allocated to each move. To determine the status of the identified moves, Hüttner's (2010) classification model was applied. According to this model, moves occurring in 90–100% of the corpus are considered obligatory, those appearing in 50–89% are classified as core, while moves occurring in 30–49% are regarded as ambiguous. Moves appearing in 1–29% of the corpus are considered optional. Because this model evaluates moves across the full range of frequency distribution, it provides a systematic framework for determining the rhetorical status of moves in the victory speeches analysed.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1. Moves in Victory Speeches

Table 1 delineates the identified moves and their corresponding sub-moves in the data set. A total of 4 unique moves were observed in the data, and these are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Move structure of the VSs

MOVES	RHETORICAL NAMES
MOVE 1	Saluting
MOVE 2	Thanking
Step 1	<i>God</i>
Step 2	<i>Electorates</i>
Step 3	<i>Electoral Commission</i>
Step 4	<i>Security service</i>
Step 5	<i>For democratic stewardship</i>
Step 6	<i>Media</i>
Step 7	<i>Family</i>
Step 8	<i>Fallen party heroes</i>
MOVE 3	Appealing to the audience
Step 1	<i>Party faithful</i>
MOVE 4	Closing

Table 1 delineates the move structure identified in the VSs analysed. Four recurrent and functionally distinct moves were observed across the dataset, indicating a relatively stable rhetorical organisation of the genre. Move 1 (Saluting) typically occurs at the opening stage of the speeches and functions to acknowledge formal protocols and establish a respectful interactional frame. Move 2 (Thanking) is the most elaborated move, comprising eight sub-moves that sequentially acknowledge divine agency, institutional actors, collective stakeholders, and personal affiliations. The density and breadth of this move suggest that gratitude serves as a central legitimising strategy in VSs, allowing speakers to distribute credit widely and symbolically reinforce democratic accountability.

Move 3 (Appealing to the audience) is realised through direct engagement with party faithful, signalling unity, continuity, and mobilisation following electoral success. Although less elaborately structured, this move performs an important persuasive function by consolidating in-group solidarity. Move 4 (Closing) marks the terminal phase of the speeches and functions to formally signal completion, often reinforcing the overarching tone of reconciliation and forward-looking leadership.

4.1.1 Move 1: Saluting

Across the four speeches analysed, it was observed that the presidents-elect used the saluting move to open communication with the electorate. The saluting move signals the beginning and the theme of the event (Liu,2012). Excerpts 1 and 2 exemplify how the saluting move appears in the data.

1. "Fellow Ghanaians" (JEAM)
2. "Ladies and gentlemen of the media, fellow Ghanaians....." (NADAA)

In relation to Liu's (2005) assertion, the saluting move occupies the initial position of the text. Two of the texts selected for the study had a salutation move, which accounted for 50% of the data. Thus, it is considered a core element. To salute the audience and create a welcoming atmosphere for the event's start, the presidents use the linguistic pattern "*fellow Ghanaians*" and "*ladies and gentlemen of the media, fellow Ghanaians*", as seen in Excerpts 1 and 2. The communicative purpose of the saluting move in the speeches supports Leech's (1983) notion that salutations serve to connect people socially. In the initial stages of their speeches, presidents salute the audience to set the scene and open the channel of communication. It is not surprising that Move 1 (Saluting) occurred 2 (50%) times across the four speeches. The presence of the saluting move reflects the conventional opening strategy observed in many formal political speeches.

4.1.2 Move 2: Thanking

The Thanking Move consistently appeared as the second move in the sequence across the speeches. This move conveyed the event's central theme. Move 2 is obligatory, as it appears in all the speeches and therefore has a 100% frequency of occurrence. Unlike Move 1, there were eight sub-moves identified under Move 2 (Thanking) (see Table 1).

Step 1: Thanking God

All the presidents referred to God as their source of strength and victory. This reflects the strong presence of religious discourse in Ghanaian public communication. Both presidents thanked God for His blessings, favour and grace. Akoto (2016) argues that politicians praise God in their speeches to recognise the existence of an Almighty Being greater than themselves and to acknowledge His direction and protection over their lives. The presidents-elect express gratitude to God to portray themselves as believers in God's supremacy. The excerpts below are examples of this sub-move:

3. "I would like to express my thanks to God for all he has done for me." (JAK)
4. "..... let us give thanks to the Almighty for seeing us through this year's general election." (JEAM)
5. "I thank the Almighty God for the life of each and every Ghanaian." (JDM)
6. "I thank Almighty God for His grace and favour in granting victory to the NPP and myself in this election. As His Word says in the Book of Holy Scripture in Ecclesiastes chapter 3 verse 11, "He has made everything beautiful in its time." (NADAA)

In Excerpts 3, 4, 5, and 6, the four presidents demonstrated that they could succeed only with God’s goodness and mercy. Given Ghana’s socio-religious background, mentioning God’s name in speeches is not unusual. References to God reflect the religious discourse commonly observed in Ghanaian public communication. This is because the presidents are aware that many Ghanaians hold similar religious convictions. The invocation of God functions rhetorically to align the speaker with widely shared religious references in public discourse. In doing so, it fosters a sense of unity and solidarity among citizens, particularly those with religious inclinations. The occurrence of this sub-move supports Liu’s (2012) findings that American presidents invoke religious authority in their inaugural addresses. Given Ghana’s diverse religious traditions, Ghanaian politicians frequently appeal to voters’ religious sensitivities (Afful & Gyasi, 2020).

Step 2: Thanking the Electorate

Another sub-move embedded in *Move 2* is *Thanking the Electorate*, deployed for *acknowledgement and present* in all four speeches. This step in *Move 2* enables the president-elect to express gratitude to voters who participated in the election. It acknowledges the voters’ role in the democratic process and recognises the support they provide in selecting the president-elect. This sub-move helps establish a sense of appreciation and connection with the audience. Interestingly, this sub-rhetorical unit was realised differently in the four speeches. Thus, this sub-move was realised in *Step 2* of JAK and JEAM speeches, but in Steps 1 and 4 of JDM and NADAA speeches, respectively. This means that these presidents accorded prominence to the Ghanaian people who voted them into power; hence, they were appreciated first. The excerpts below illustrate this step:

7. “I would next like to thank Ghanaians. Your faith in multi-party democracy, your patience and fortitude in the face of so many challenges have brought us here to this momentous day.” (JAK)
8. “I want to thank you for giving me the mandate to manage the affairs of the state after January 7th 2009. I accept the onerous responsibility with all humility.” (JEAM)
9. “..... But most importantly, I wish to thank the voters of Ghana who turned out in their record numbers to exercise the right of choice.” (JDM)
10. “There has never been a more humbling moment in my life, and I thank you, the good people of Ghana, for this massive show of support and the confidence you have reposed in me and my party.” (NADAA)

The four presidents demonstrate their commitment to upholding the trust placed in them by promising to carry out their duties to the best of their ability. Their expressions of gratitude to Ghanaians represent a new era of government that brings positive reforms and focuses on the needs of the Ghanaian people. In their speeches, only NADAA mentioned his party, the NPP, as shown in excerpt 10; the other three presidents did not. This is understandable as this pattern may reflect the broader unifying orientation of victory speeches, where speakers foreground national identity rather than partisan affiliation. Thus, everyone who cast a ballot in Ghana at the time knew that a specific party had won the presidential election. As a result, JAK, JEAM, and JDM deployed language that cooperatively engages their audience. This presupposes that complimenting the various

parties would not advance the speech's unifying agenda. In other words, the presidency should be understood as a unifying institution that fulfils duties expected by the populace. Again, JDM accords considerable weight to the voters who elected him as president by using the linguistic expression '*Most importantly*' to emphasise their central role in his electoral victory, as seen in excerpt 9.

Step 3: Thanking the Electoral Commission

This sub-move was also observed in Move 2. It appears in step 2 of both JDM and NADAA, but occurs in step 4 of JEAM's speech and step 6 of JAK's. The electoral system ensures that elections are conducted in a structured and organised manner. It includes various measures that uphold transparency and integrity in the electoral process, such as voter registration, ballot counting, and result certification. The Electoral Commission's recognition emphasises the institution's role in managing elections and rhetorically reinforces the legitimacy of the electoral process. In their VSs, the presidents aim to unite the nation, regardless of party allegiance. The reference to the Electoral Commission and election supervisors rhetorically focuses the institutional integrity of the electoral process and emphasises the peaceful conduct of the elections. Below are selected excerpts illustrating this step in the speeches.

11. *"To the Chairman of the Electoral Commission, the members of the Commission and the staff, I say well done. I hope that the problems encountered in the December 28th run-off election will form a basis for continuous improvement in our electoral process."* (JAK)
12. *"I thank the Electoral Commissioner and his team for guiding the nation through a very tough electoral process."* (JEAM)
13. *"I want to thank the electoral commission ...who helped maintain law and order."* (JDM)
14. *"The Electoral Commission, under its new leadership, with Charlotte Osei in the Chair, is to be congratulated for organizing this credible election. She and the Commission have allayed the fears of many about their capacity to conduct a good election. This election has contributed to strengthening the principles of democratic accountability in our body politic, and the Commission will take a considerable part of the credit for that welcome outcome."* (NADAA)

Excerpts 11-14 show that all four presidents were aware of the cumbersome nature of electoral administration and of the Electoral Commission's key role in elections. They all praised the Commission for the conduct of the elections.

Step 4: Thanking the Security Service

This sub-move was also found in all the selected speeches. It recognised the security services and civilians in the country, and the roles they play in maintaining peace during elections. The following excerpts illustrate this sub-move:

15. *"I would also wish to thank all security and civil services."* (JAK)

Ebenezer Asare
Kwasi Sarfo-Adu
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“Rhetorical Moves in Presidential Victory
Speeches: Spotlighting a Non-native Speaker
Context”

16. *“I also thank the security agencies for the important role they have played in the process.”* (JEAM)
17. *“I want to thank ...our security service personnel who helped maintain law and order.”* (JDM)
18. *“Our security services are to be commended for ensuring generally peaceful conduct of the poll, and doing so in a professional manner. That is what the nation expects of them.”* (NADAA)

In Excerpt 15, JAK addressed the security service. The acknowledgement of security agencies foregrounds their role in maintaining peace and stability during the electoral process. Again, JEAM and NADAA, in Excerpts 16 and 18, respectively, congratulated the security forces on maintaining a peaceful environment during the election period.

Step 5: Thanking for Democratic Stewardship

All four politicians used this sub-move to express gratitude to key stakeholders, including their predecessors, senior citizens, the council of elders, and party loyalists, for their contributions to the electoral victory. The following excerpts illustrate how this step was realised in the speeches:

19. *“My thanks also go to His Excellency, President Rawlings, who, at the end of his mandated term under a democratic constitution, has presided over this historic election.”* (JAK)
20. *“President John Agyekum Kufuor has in no small way helped broaden Ghana’s democratic dispensation. And his willingness to hand over to me come Wednesday, January 07, 2009, is a plus to him personally and to Ghana as a nation. I congratulate President Kufuor.”* (JEAM)
21. *“I wish to thank our party executives from the national level to the polling station level for their hard work. I wish to thank members of our council of elders and the founder of our party, Jerry Rawlings and indeed all activists and cavers of our party who worked day and night to ensure this victory.”* (JDM)
22. *“To members and sympathizers of the great Elephant family, to our illustrious former President of the Republic, His Excellency John Agyekum Kufuor, to our founding members, leading figures, members of party organs, parliamentary candidates and Members of Parliament, current and past national officers, regional, constituency...I say a big thank you to each and every one of you for your hard work, commitment and encouragement, and for your belief in me and in my leadership of our party over the last 8 years.”* (NADAA)

Under this sub-move, not only were the predecessors and party faithful acknowledged, but the entire population was as well. None of the speakers made any partisan references. All citizens of the country, regardless of their political party, were accorded the necessary honour and appreciation for their support. Interestingly, even opposition candidates who lost the elections were acknowledged and thanked for their good fight. This gesture goes beyond mere politeness; it offers moral support by affirming the value of their participation, promoting national unity, and reinforcing democratic ideals of mutual respect and inclusion. This is illustrated in Excerpts 23-26:

23. "..... I would like to thank His Excellency, Vice-President John Atta Mills for his gracious concession (JAK)
24. *The final leg involved me and Nana Akuffo Addo, a worthy son of our nation. I congratulate him and all others for a keenly fought contest"* (JEAM)
25. *"I am grateful to have had the opportunity to engage with my fellow candidates in both, and I will like to say to them, though we have stood as opponents on what appears to be different sides of a divide, at the end of the day, we all are standing on the same side of our beloved mother Ghana...."* (JDM)
26. *"The President of the Republic and the NDC presidential candidate, H.E. John Dramani Mahama..... I thanked him for this graceful gesture, which is in the finest traditions of Ghanaian statesmanship and, on my part, assured him of my cooperation for a successful transition. I have also received words of congratulation from my other competitors... I am grateful to them"* (NADAA).

As seen in Excerpt 26, NADAA devoted adequate textual space to acknowledge and thank JDM, who was the immediate past president and the only sitting president to lose an election in the fourth republic. For this reason, it was necessary to recognise and appreciate JDM to win over the audience, especially those on the opposition side. The religious leaders were also acknowledged. This step was observed in only JDM and NADAA's *Thanking moves*. The two personalities thanked the religious leaders for the prayers offered for the country's peaceful, free, and fair election. This step is illustrated in Excerpts 27 and 28:

27. *"I wish to thank religious leaders; Christians, Muslims of every faith."* (JDM)
28. *"To the numerous priests and imams who have prayed for my soul and who have taken the trouble to intercede with the Almighty on my behalf, amongst them, Cardinal Emeritus Peter Akwasi Sarpong...."* (NADAA)

JDM and NADAA are aware that Ghana has multiple religions and address citizens accordingly. Mentioning *Christians, Muslims of every faith, and the numerous priests and imams* in Extracts 27 and 28 is reasonable, given Ghana's divergent religious views and beliefs. Hence, the presidents decided to use religiously neutral language. JDM again, in Extract 28, thanked the traditional leaders, chiefs, community elders, and many Ghanaian citizens across the country who welcomed him into their cities, towns, and villages and made him feel at home. Surprisingly, this was observed only in JDM's victory speech.

Step 6: Thanking the Media

To provide information, analysis, and coverage of the political proceedings on election day, media involvement is crucial. Three of the presidents—JEAM, JDM, and NADAA—acknowledged the role of the media. Below are excerpts from the speeches:

29. *"The media deserve our commendation for helping Ghanaians keep a close eye on the election."* (JEAM)
30. *"I want to thank the media for the coverage they gave all of us. Without the media, our messages would not have gotten to the electorate. I want to thank the media; you did a fantastic job. God bless you."* (JDM)

Ebenezer Asare
Kwasi Sarfo-Adu
Benjamin Amoakohene
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“Rhetorical Moves in Presidential Victory
Speeches: Spotighting a Non-native Speaker
Context”

31. *“I take this opportunity to thank you, members of the Ghanaian media, for your continuing engagement in the public interest of our country. Your vigilance and activism are now by-words in the consistent efforts our people are making to carve a secure, democratic future for themselves. Senior journalists like Abdul Malik Kweku Baako, Gina Blay, Egbert Faibille.....”* (NADAA)

The acknowledgements by these three presidents to the media are unsurprising for several reasons. First, the media inform the public about the election process, including polling locations, voting procedures, and candidate profiles. They further provide voters with important information to help them make informed choices. Moreover, the media covers the election, including voter turnout, potential issues at the polls, and provisional results. Ultimately, they cover any newsworthy events or developments that could affect the election, such as legal challenges or voter irregularities. It is not surprising that, in Excerpt 30, JDM thanked the media for their coverage during the election period. JDM also used the expression *“keen eye on the election”* to imply that, to keep the public informed about the election’s status and results, the media is essential for providing real-time reporting as results become available. NADAA carefully used words that convey respect to acknowledge ace journalists for their sustained engagement in the public interest of the country and for their admirable standards of professionalism and ethical conduct, which should be emulated by future generations (see Excerpt 31).

Step 7: Thanking the Family

All the presidents, except JEAM, thanked their respective families for the key role these family members play in these presidents’ quest to become the first gentlemen of Ghana. All the speakers used expressions of gratitude to emphasise a sense of togetherness and unity within their respective families. The words of gratitude indicate that the families were firmly behind these presidents’ respective visions and aspirations to become the first gentleman of Ghana. Additionally, thanking the families helps convey a stable and grounded image to the public. Excerpts 32-34 project instances of this step in the speeches:

32. *“I would like to thank my entire family, especially my wife, Theresa, for the support I have enjoyed from them in the struggle.”* (JAK)

33. *“I must thank my wife not least of all for the ginger and honey. I must thank my wife and members of my family for their unwavering support and encouragement.”* (JDM)

34. *“And to my beautiful wife, my beloved Rebecca, who waged such a great campaign in her own right, my daughters, Gyankroma, Valerie, Dokua, my sister Marigold, my brother Edward, and my entire family, I, firstly, must apologise for taking you on this rollercoaster ride. I am, however, very grateful for the love and support you have given me, and for standing shoulder to shoulder with me through the years till now. Long may it so continue.”* (NADAA)

In Excerpts 32-34, the presidents-elect express appreciation to their family members for their steadfast support during the campaign. Expressions of gratitude directed toward family members emphasise the supportive role of close relatives within the political journey of the speakers. Surprisingly, JAK, JDM, and NADAA express their special gratitude to

their respective wives, who provided the support needed throughout the campaign period. Thus, JAK, JDM, and NADAA recognised the moral support, a listening ear, and words of encouragement provided by their partners during the trying times of the election. To show appreciation to the family, JDM and NADAA acknowledged their wives before their families, as seen in Extracts 33 and 34, respectively, but this was contrary to JAK, who mentioned the entire family first but still gave prominence to the wife by using the expression, “*especially to my wife, Theresah....*”, as exemplified in Excerpt 32.

Step 8: Acknowledging Fallen Party Heroes

In addition to the sub-rhetorical units identified in the data, the last step realised in *Move 2* in the speeches is *Acknowledging Fallen Party Heroes*. This step was seen in the speeches of NADAA and JDM. Using this rhetorical sub-unit, the presidents acknowledged the efforts of their fallen party heroes who died for or before the cause of the campaign. The speakers explicate this in the excerpts below:

35. “*Let me pause to remember colleagues who fell in the course of our campaign – Adams Mahama, Otanka Obetsebi-Lampsey, J.B. Danquah Adu, Peter Wiafe Peprah, Abubakar Saddique, Kwabena Boadu, and others. May their souls continue to rest in perfect peace in the bosom of the Almighty until the last day of the Resurrection, when we shall all meet again. Amen.*” (NADAA)
36. “*This year, we have experienced pain and loss, we have suffered the unusual tragedy of losing two of our leaders within months of each other. The sudden and untimely death of our sitting president Professor John Evans Atta Mills left all of us shaking. We mourned together and we faced the uncertainties posed by these peculiar circumstances together. Through, our unity, we were both able to express and ease our grief. Just as it seemed we have found our footing and started to once again feel as thou we were on solid ground; we were struck by the blow of another death. That of our former Vice-President, Alhaji Aliu Mahama. Once again, we supported one another as we mourned our collective loss.*” (JDM)

NADAA acknowledges and honours party members who lost their lives during the party’s electoral campaign, using personal naming as a strategy to memorialise sacrifice and reinforce party solidarity. He acknowledged the effort, commitment, and ultimate sacrifice of these fallen heroes in supporting the campaign that led to the election of NADAA as president of Ghana. The reference to fallen party heroes introduces an emotional dimension to the speech and reinforces collective memory within the political community. It also evokes feelings of empathy and patriotism. With this, the president-elect establishes a connection with the audience by tapping into their emotions. It fosters a strong emotional bond and upholds the values and principles associated with the fallen heroes, as seen in Excerpt 35. For unity’s sake, JDM paid his respects to the departed souls in his speech. Thus, he strategically revered Professor John Evans Atta Mills, the former president and presidential candidate of the National Democratic Congress, and Alhaji Aliu Mahama, the former Vice-President of Ghana, both of whom were members of the New Patriotic Party (see Excerpt 36). Additionally, JDM encourages Ghanaians to demonstrate comparable loyalty and commitment. He indicates that the victory was due to team effort and individual sacrifices rather than to his own win. It does not come as a surprise when

JDM dedicates the victory to the late Professor John Evans Atta Mills in the latter part of his speech. This was realised in Excerpt 37:

37. *“Finally, as I promised during the campaign, I wish to dedicate this victory to the memory of Professor John Evans Atta Mills, and I wish to pledge that we shall continue the good works that he started.”* (JDM)

It is vital to reiterate this important campaign pledge — that is, JDM’s promise to honour the legacy of the late Professor John Evans Atta Mills by continuing his good works — to the audience during the victory speech. This act of reiterating campaign pledges in political discourse, such as in victory speeches, serves as a change agent or reinforces existing beliefs (Mirzaei et al., 2016).

4.1.3 Move 3: *Appealing to the Audience*

In this move, the speakers call on citizens to fulfil their role as loyal citizens. Here, the presidents, in their speeches, encourage nonpartisan politics while stressing the need for unity in governance. This move was present in all the speeches (100%) and was, therefore, classified as an obligatory move, reflecting its central role in fulfilling the genre’s communicative purpose. The rhetorical unit, *appealing to the Audience*, is characterised by one sub-rhetorical unit, *Appealing to Party Faithfuls*. This sub-move in *MOVE 3* was absent from the JAK dataset. The excerpts below illustrate Move 3 (*Appealing to the Audience*):

38. *“.....In conclusion, I ask all of you for your prayers and support for the incoming government and myself. We are at the start of a brand-new century, and with your support, we can all work to make it the Ghanaian Century.”* (JAK).
39. *“The election is over, and there is only one Ghana; there is no NDC Ghana and NPP Ghana. I renew my pledge that I will be President of all Ghanaians..... Change has also come to Ghana; let us all embrace it and forge ahead together with a common sense of purpose. Let us all put our shoulders to the wheel and begin to build a Better Ghana.”* (JEAM)
40. *“Ladies and Gentlemen, I urge everyone to take this opportunity to come together to move out of the spirit of competition and move now into the spirit of cooperation. There is much work to be done. The issues and challenges that face our nations have no allegiances, they cut across lines of political affiliation, religious and ethnic background, social class and regional location. Indeed, they affect all of us. We cannot afford to be enemies of our own progress; we cannot afford to stand divided.....”* (JDM)
41. *“Fellow Ghanaians..... I am confident, and I have faith that, with God’s guidance and your active help and hardwork, we will move our country forward. Together, we will change Ghana, and use all the blessings that the Almighty has bestowed on us to bring prosperity to our people and nation in our time. Together, we will fulfil the destiny of Ghana, the destiny of freedom, justice and prosperity that the ancestors and founders of our nation defined for us.”* (NADAA)

Move 3 (Appealing to the Audience) is important for presidents in VSs as it seeks to inspire and unite the nation towards a common goal. This move involves addressing citizens' hopes, aspirations, and concerns while outlining the president's vision and plans, as demonstrated in Excerpts 38-41.

Step 1: Appealing to Party Faithfuls

The results showed that this sub-move was in *Move 3*. While this step was absent from JAK's speech, it was present in the speeches of JEAM, JDM, and NADAA. The primary purpose of this Step is to encourage party supporters to celebrate the victory with caution. Instances of the realisation of this sub-move are illustrated in the excerpts below:

42. *"Members of the NDC have cause to celebrate but I am appealing to them to be extremely moderate and circumspect and not be provocative in their actions."* (JEAM)
43. *"Let me also say that I am informed that victory celebrations will be held in other regions. I wish to call on all who will participate including our supporters to be restrained in those celebrations. Let's celebrate this victory together as a nation. Let's not be provocative, this is a victory for all Ghanaians not only the N.D.C party."* (JDM)
44. *"Whilst this occasion would understandably lead to widespread jubilation amongst party supporters, I entreat them to respect the peace and the property and lives of everybody, especially those of our political opponents. We are the party of the rule of law, and we should act accordingly with magnanimity in our moment of victory."* (NADAA)

192

Excerpts 42-44 project that the presidents want to avoid party differences or arouse resentment from those who might be upset or disheartened by the election results, so they advise the supporters to celebrate responsibly. In doing so, the presidents-elect express a wish for peace and promote a more inclusive, united society. Again, the presidents stressed that the election was over and there was no need for partisan politics. The presidents demonstrate a commitment to representing every citizen, including those who did not support their candidacy (see Excerpt 43), by advising all Ghanaians to be prudent in their celebrations. It is an appeal to supporters to approach victory with humility and to recognise the diversity of opinions in the country.

4.14 Move 4: Closing

This move signals the end of the event and was realised briefly across the speeches. It occurred in all four speeches (100%) and was therefore classified as an obligatory move, with all speakers invoking religious authority in the closing. The excerpts below exemplify how this move was realised in the speeches.

45. *"God Bless Ghana, God bless us all. Thank you."* (JAK)
46. *"May God continue to bless our homeland Ghana, and make Her great and strong."* (JEAM)
47. *"I thank you all very much and God bless all of you. Thank you."* (JDM)

48. “God bless our homeland Ghana and make our nation great and strong”.
 “The battle is still the Lord’s”
 “Onyankopon nhyira mu nyinaa” (God bless you all)
 “Nyɔɔhmɔ ajɔɔ nye fɛɛ” (God bless you all)
 “Mawu ne yira mi” (God bless you)
 “Allah i saa muku Albarka” (God bless you)
 “Thank you.” (NADAA)

The *Closing Move* showed a great call to the Supreme Being. Thus, resorting to religious power is a feature of the VSs’ last move. The element of code-switching was seen in NADAA’s conclusion [see Excerpt 48]. The use of code-switching introduces multilingual expressions that symbolically acknowledge Ghana’s linguistic diversity. He switched to speaking four local languages—*Twi, Ga, Ewe, and Hausa*. All the words he used were gratitude-related. This is an optional style, since it has already been established that VSs, like other political speeches, are rendered in English. Nevertheless, code-switching is a linguistic resource that will leave a good mark on the audience.

4.2. Textual Space

The significance of a move is determined by the amount of textual space allotted to it (Afful, 2005). To calculate the textual space of each move, we run a word count for each move over the dataset. Table 2 displays the overall count and percentage of words assigned to each move.

Table 2: Distribution of textual space of the moves

Move	Textual space in words	Percentage (%)
M1: Saluting	25	0.59%
M2: Thanking	3095	73.55%
M3: Appealing to the Audience	1014	24.10%
M4: Closing	74	1.76%
Total	4208	100.00%

The distribution of textual space across the moves reveals apparent differences in their functional weight within the victory speeches. *Move 2 (Thanking)* accounts for the most significant proportion of the corpus, comprising 3,095 words (73.55%), indicating that expressions of gratitude are the core communicative activity of the genre. This extensive allocation of textual space reflects the importance of acknowledging supporters, party members, and stakeholders in legitimising electoral success and fostering post-election unity. *Move 3 (Appealing to the Audience)* accounts for 1,014 words (24.10%), suggesting that persuasive and unifying appeals also play a significant role, though secondary to thanking. In contrast, *Move 1 (Saluting)* and *Move 4 (Closing)* occupy minimal textual space, with 25 words (0.59%) and 74 words (1.76%) respectively, reflecting their primarily ceremonial and boundary-marking functions rather than substantive rhetorical development. The distribution demonstrates that while salutations and closings are

structurally necessary, the communicative emphasis of Ghanaian presidential VSs lies predominantly in thanking and appealing moves.

Top of Form

Bottom of Form

4.3 Sequencing of Moves

Move sequencing is a significant rhetorical strategy employed by experts of “genre” to ensure coherence and effectiveness in communication. It refers to the order in which rhetorical moves are arranged to accomplish specific communicative purposes. According to genre scholars such as Swales (1990), Dudley-Evans (1994), and Hyland (2004), the sequence of moves in a text can reflect both linearity, in which moves occur in a set order, and cyclicity, in which certain moves may recur for emphasis or elaboration. In the current study, all four presidential VSs follow a linear four-move structure: Saluting Move → Thanking Move → Appealing to Audience Move → Closing Move (1 > 2 > 3 > 4).

This consistent sequencing suggests a shared rhetorical convention in the Ghanaian political context, in which each president strategically progresses from greeting the audience to expressing gratitude, addressing the general public, and finally closing the speech. For example, in Akufo-Addo’s speech, the salutation (“Fellow Ghanaians...”) is immediately followed by appreciation to voters, party members, and supporters. This transitions into an appeal for national unity and inclusive development, before concluding with a call to the Supreme Being. Similarly, Mahama’s VS follows the same structure, maintaining linearity without overlapping or skipping any moves.

194

This linear progression contributes to the clarity and persuasiveness of the speeches. It also reflects the genre’s ceremonial and formal nature, aligning with audience expectations in a high-stakes political context. The absence of cyclical patterns or move shifts further supports the conclusion that Ghanaian VSs are tightly structured and designed for maximal rhetorical impact at a specific moment of political transition. The consistency in sequencing across the dataset underscores the conventionalisation of this genre in Ghana’s Fourth Republic. It also highlights the influence of institutional and cultural norms in shaping the rhetorical organisation of presidential communication.

5 Conclusion

This study examined the rhetorical organisation of presidential victory speeches delivered by Ghanaian presidents of the Fourth Republic. Drawing on Swales’ (1990) genre theory and Hüttner’s (2010) model for determining move status, the analysis identified a consistent four-move structure: saluting, thanking, appealing to the audience, and closing. The sequencing of these moves follows a linear pattern (1 > 2 > 3 > 4), suggesting a relatively stable rhetorical organisation within the genre. Code-switching was also observed in the closing of President Akufo-Addo’s speech, indicating the presence of multilingual rhetorical strategies in Ghanaian presidential discourse.

DOI:

The findings contribute to research on political discourse, presidential communication, and genre studies. In particular, the identification of a four-move structure provides insight into how Ghanaian presidents organise victory speeches to acknowledge stakeholders, promote unity, and frame the transition into governance. The results also have pedagogical implications for English for Specific Purposes (ESP), where the identified move structure may serve as a model for analysing and teaching the organisation of political speeches. In addition, the presence of code-switching highlights the role of linguistic and cultural resources in shaping political communication within multilingual societies.

This study is limited by the size of the dataset, which comprises four victory speeches delivered by presidents of Ghana’s Fourth Republic. The selection was restricted to the first victory speeches of presidents-elect to ensure contextual comparability. Because victory speeches occur only once after a successful election, the number of available texts is limited. Future research may examine additional electoral cycles, later victory speeches of the same presidents, or comparable political contexts in other African democracies to further examine the schematic patterns identified in this study.

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